

A STUDY OF THE USE OF PERCEPTUAL FEATURES FOR MUSIC EMOTION RECOGNITION

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ABSTRACT

Perceptual features are defined as musical descriptors that closely match a listener's understanding of musical characteristics. This paper tackles Music Emotion Recognition through the consideration of three kinds of perceptual feature sets, human rated, computational and modelled features. The human rated features are extracted through a survey and the computational features are estimated directly from the audio signal. Regressive modelling is used to predict the human rated features from the computational features. The latter predicted set constitute the modelled features. The regressive models performed well for all features except for Harmony, Timbre and Melody. All three feature sets are used to train three regression models (one for each set) to predict the components Energy and Valence, which are then used to recognise emotion. The model trained on the rated features performed well for both components. This therefore shows that emotion can be predicted from perceptual features. The models trained on the computational and modelled features performed well in predicting Energy, but not so well in predicting Valence. This is not surprising since the main predictors for Valence are Melody, Harmony and Timbre, which therefore need added or modified computational features that better match human perception.

1. INTRODUCTION

Music feature extraction has traditionally been tackled top-down, using textual, descriptive metadata; or bottom-up, using low-level audio signal descriptors, from which musical concepts may be derived. Unclear or misleading connections between low-level descriptors of the acoustical data, higher level descriptors of the associated musical features, and textual metadata are converging to a boundary that has not yet been overcome. This is termed the *semantic gap* [1].

Studies have shown that several of the shortcomings of the purely data driven techniques can be overcome by applying musical knowledge [1]. It has been proposed that

cultural and editorial metadata, currently used by consumers for finding the music they like, be replaced by semantic descriptors within musical dimensions such as rhythm and timbre [2]. The use of meaningful descriptors pushes the *glass ceiling* for music classification to levels higher than originally anticipated for previous data-driven approaches.

This paper undertakes the task of Music Emotion Recognition (MER) through Computational, Rated and Modelled perceptual features. In this paper, the term *feature* is used to denote a particular characteristic of a musical extract. Features were either estimated directly from the audio signal by signal-processing tools, rated perceptually by listeners, or modelled using pattern recognition algorithms. To distinguish between the three groups, they will be called Computational, Rated and Modelled features respectively, to emphasise their respective derivation approach. A dataset of musical extracts was compiled for this purpose.

This study goes a step beyond the current trend in MER of classifying emotion directly from the available computational features or social tags. Rated features are modelled from Computational features and then used in the MER task. The reason behind this step is to reduce the large number of proposed features in the literature to a smaller list of features that can be distinguished by music listeners, irrespective of their musical background. The performance of the different feature sets is compared through the task of music emotion classification.

Section 2 gives an overview on related work in the area. Section 3 describes the framework built for this study and gives an overview of each processing block. Observations and results of every processing block are given in Section 4. A brief discussion follows in Section 5 and conclusions are drawn in Section 6.

2. RELATED WORK

Psychological studies have shown that emotions conveyed by music are objective enough to be valid for mathematical modelling [3]. The main efforts of emotion-based music retrieval have focused on discovering signal features that are correlated with the affective scores. In order to classify music emotion, preference is given to selecting those features directly related to the human perception of music [4].

Cook [5] states that the musical aspects that humans use to describe music are pitch, loudness, duration, timbre, style and texture. However, the information directly repre-

sented in the acoustic signal is only the physical property of music, such as absolute pitch and note duration. Herrera et al. [2] propose the incorporation of higher-level semantic descriptors to a given feature set. They describe semantic descriptors as measures that can be computed directly from the audio signal, by means of the combination of signal processing, machine learning techniques, and musical knowledge. Their goal is to emphasise the musical attributes of audio signals (such as rhythm and instrumentation), attaining higher levels of semantic complexity than low-level features (such as spectral centroid and spectral flux), but without being restricted by the rules of music notation, since human music perception retrieves information that might be different from traditional concepts of music theory.

The approach taken by Hedblad [6] for the modelling of perceptual music descriptors, was to include all extracted features as potential predictors and apply the stepwise version of linear regression. However, non-linear relationships were not taken into account during the modelling process. In other areas of Music Information Retrieval (MIR), Support Vector Regression (SVR) and Classification (SVC) is a widely used supervised learning classification algorithm. It has been found superior to other machine learning methods in a number of studies [7–9].

3. METHODOLOGY

The framework built for this study is shown in Figure 1 depicting each processing block as well as input and output data as required for each phase. Each processing block is further explained in the following sub-sections.

3.1 Dataset Selection

Figure 2 displays the Energy-Valence (EV) Model for Emotion which was built for this study. It is based on Thayer’s two-dimensional emotion model [10], with descriptors from Russell’s circumplex model of affect [11] and their adaptations, which were used in [3, 4, 9, 12, 13]. An emotive descriptor was chosen for the horizontal and vertical axes and each diagonal. The chosen descriptors were simple and distinct adjectives to avoid ambiguity. Using this model, the dataset was chosen such that the selected music clips would be uniformly distributed across the Energy-Valence plane.

Four online music databases which offer a search by mood (All Music Guide [14], Last.fm [15], Spotify [16] and Stereomood [17]) were identified. These were also used in other published work related to MER [3, 9, 13]. The first five songs suggested by each database for every emotion were selected. A thirty-second segment was then manually extracted from the refrain. During this process, the music clips were converted to a uniform format (44,100 Hz, 16 bits, stereo PCM WAV) and normalised to the same volume level. Clips were amplified such that the peak amplitude was 0dB. Two-second fade-in and fade-outs were introduced to improve the listening experience. The music clips were kept in their original form, irrespective of whether they were instrumental or included lyrics, since

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of the framework built for the required tests and analysis, depicting each processing block as well as input and output data as required for each phase. Two instances of regression were performed. The first ($Regression_{PF}$), describes the modelling of Rated features through the Computational ones. The second regression process ($Regression_{EV}$), describes modelling of the Energy and Valence emotive components through three separate feature sets.

changing instrumentation was considered as changing the listening experience, a fact that might have a negative effect on the modelling and classification phases. The dataset was then fine tuned to ensure emotion consistency in the music clips, discarding excerpts with explicit and dominant positive or negative lyrics that would influence the ratings and limiting overly familiar songs. The final dataset was composed of seventy, thirty-second music extracts.

3.2 The Subjective Test

A subjective test was conducted through a computer-based survey. It was distributed by email to volunteers who showed interest in completing it. While they were instructed to complete it in a quiet environment it was not run in a controlled environment, in order to approximate the participant’s preferred music-listening habits. Each survey participant was asked to listen to thirty-five music clips played in random order. Each participant had to grade each music clip using eleven music features. This was done through a slider with extremes at each end, as depicted in Figure 3. To calculate the mean rating, the slider position was later translated to an integer between

Figure 2: The Energy-Valence Model for Emotion that was compiled for this study. Simple and distinct emotive descriptors were selected.

1 and 7, with 4 being regarded as the neutral rating. The test structure was based on similar rating tests for perceptual features [18, 19]. Features in these tests were in turn inspired by previous published work [20]. The Rated music features were nine perceptual features (Pitch, Modality, Harmony, Melody, Speed, Rhythm, Articulation, Dynamics and Timbre) and two emotive descriptors ($Energy_{Rated}$ and $Valence_{Rated}$), as detailed in [21]. A brief explanation and ten-second samples were given to the participants in an introductory screen.

Each music clip was also labelled using one of the eight emotions given in Figure 2. This was achieved using a drop-down menu. The aim of these two approaches was to confirm that consistent emotive results would be obtained. In order to calculate the average response of the emotive descriptor, each descriptor was translated to a pair of co-ordinates such as to represent their circular distribution as shown in Figure 2. The descriptor was split in two components representing the Energy and Valence dimensions. These components will further be referenced as $Energy_{Mood}$ and $Valence_{Mood}$ respectively. This split facilitates the comparison with the linear ratings, further referenced as $Energy_{Rated}$ and $Valence_{Rated}$.

The seventy music extracts were split in two groups of thirty-five clips, both uniformly distributed along the EV model. Thirty participants rated one of these two groups. Another five participants voluntarily rated the whole dataset, rating each group on different days. Eighteen participants were males and seventeen were females and they were aged between 22 and 63 (average age of 35). Twelve had never practised or studied music, eight had basic or informal music training and fifteen had advanced music background.

3.3 Computational Feature Extraction

Four tools (Essentia [22], MIRtoolbox [23], PsySound3 [24] and Sonic Annotator [25]) were chosen to extract 118 Computational features that may be used to approximate perceptual features, as detailed in [21]. The scope of this

Figure 3: The graphical user interface used for rating the music clips in the survey.

study is not to judge the accuracy of a particular feature extraction algorithm; but rather, how close it comes to a perceptual descriptor. Feature extraction was done through a short-term window (frame) that moves chronologically along the temporal signal. The frame length varies across algorithms, but is generally in the order of tens of milliseconds with hop size (overlap) of half its length. The results were summarised by taking means and variances across the frames.

3.4 Data Analysis

Data Analysis was performed through IBM SPSS Statistics 22 [26]. For the survey results, values for Cronbach's alpha, mean inter-item correlation, histograms for mean ratings, Friedman test and error bar graphs were extracted. Dimension reduction through Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was performed after the computational feature extraction to avoid redundancy of multiple features measuring the same thing and for summarising a number of linearly highly correlating features. This reduced the number of Computational features to 62.

3.5 Feature Modelling

Models for each of the Rated features were built from the Computational features through Multiple Linear Regression (MLR), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Support Vector Regression (SVR), as depicted by $Regression_{PF}$ in Figure 1. Feature selection is incorporated in linear modelling through the Weka M5 option. For ANN and SVR, the feature selection algorithm Relief [27] was used to identify the most relevant Computational features for each of the predicted variables. The model parameters were selected through ten iterations of 10-fold cross-validation using Weka Experimenter [28]. The main statistical value that was minimised during the parameter estimation process is the root mean squared error (RMSE). Once the RMSE for a particular model was determined, the correlation coefficient r was noted. The models were compared based on these two attributes. The

Weka ZeroR classifier [28] was used to extract the mean model, taken in this study as the Baseline model.

3.6 Emotion Classification

Emotion classification was utilised as a way to compare performance of the various types of perceptual feature sets. This was performed in two steps. The first step, depicted by $Regression_{EV}$ in Figure 1, was to model the Energy and Valence components through SVR. Regression was attempted with three different feature sets: Rated (the nine features rated by the survey participants, as described in Section 3.2), Modelled (the eight features modelled through SVR, as described in Section 3.5) and Computational (sixty-two Computational features obtained after the Computational feature extraction and data reduction as described in Section 3.3).

The second step was to apply the k-means clustering algorithm on each resulting Energy-Valence model. Four clusters were extracted each time. The choice of four clusters even though there were originally eight emotive descriptors allows for some tolerance to the subjectivity of emotions.

The average song ratings for the emotion components $Energy_{Rated}$, $Valence_{Rated}$ and $Energy_{Mood}$, $Valence_{Mood}$ were used as inputs for the k-means clustering algorithm. The outputs were taken as the ground truth cluster ownership for each song. A classification was considered to be accurate when a song was clustered within the same group as the respective ground truth. Performance was compared through scatter plot distribution, cluster centroid centres, and clips included in each cluster.

4. RESULTS

4.1 The Subjective Test

Values for Cronbach's alpha varied between 0.84 (for Modality) and 0.98 (for Speed), confirming internal consistency of the survey. The p-value for the Friedman Tests for every feature was in the order between 10^{-37} and 10^{-160} , which means that all mean feature rating scores differ significantly between song extracts. However this does not imply that all of the seventy songs differ significantly from each other in every feature, but that groups (or clusters) can be identified.

Inter-rater correlation was not consistent for all features but differed according to the type of feature and difficulty of the task. Observations indicate that the more difficult the feature meaning was to grasp, the closer to the neutral rating (4) the majority of the ratings for the feature were.

The distribution of mean ratings splits the features in three groups with similar observed characteristics. Participants found features in the first group (Speed, Dynamics, Energy) to be the easiest to rate and agreed between each other to a large extent, with a mean inter-rater correlation of 0.72, 0.65 and 0.66 respectively. Values for mean ratings in this group were the furthest from the neutral rating (4), implying high agreement between raters. These three features are common adjectives for music description. They

are also the least subjective, since stating a song as being fast is independent of whether one prefers fast or slow songs.

The values for the inter-rater correlation for features in the second group (Valence, Timbre, Pitch, Melody, Harmony), were between 0.29 and 0.40. Though less common, and more subjective, participants seemed to understand the meaning of these five descriptors. Features in the third group (Articulation, Rhythm, Modality) were the hardest for listeners to rate. Their descriptions are more technical and they are the least natural for people to notice or comment about, unless one is specifically listening to that particular aspect. The observed distributions, where averages are located toward the middle of the range, is indicative of a lack of agreement between listeners. Weak inter-rater correlation was observed with values of 0.25, 0.20 and 0.26 respectively. However, though in this case these are a small minority, extremes can still be distinguished.

The results for the mean inter-rater correlations were compared with those published for a similar survey in [18], where participants all had a level of musical background. The values show that participants with considerable musical experience improve results for the more technical features (Rhythm, Modality and Articulation) but not for the others. On the other hand, keeping the original instrumentation of the music extracts improved the results for features where instrumentation is essential (Timbre, Dynamics and hence, Energy).

Linearity was confirmed between the components of the emotive descriptors ($Energy_{Mood}$ and $Valence_{Mood}$), and $Energy_{Rated}$ and $Valence_{Rated}$ respectively, with correlation values between these two pairs of attributes exceeding 0.9. The scatter plots in Figures 4 (a) and (b) illustrate that the distribution for the emotive descriptors (Figure 4 (b)) is closer to the desired circular shape. Clusters per quadrant seem identifiable, with few music clips being located towards the centre of the distribution. This indicates that there were only few cases where ratings were so varied that the calculated average was close to 0. This is a further indication of rater agreement. The scatter plot for $Energy_{Rated}$ and $Valence_{Rated}$ (Figure 4 (a)) hints at a skew in the positive diagonal, with values expected in the calm-positive quadrant overlapping the calm-negative quadrant.

4.2 Feature Analysis

Significant correlations were identified between algorithms extracting similar Computational features (refer to Section 3.3). Lack of perfect correlation was attributed to different approaches and different parameters. However, when these were compared to the Rated features, correlation was weaker. The highest correlation values between Rated and Computational features values were obtained for Dynamics (0.80), Speed (0.74) and Pitch (0.56). Articulation did not correlate significantly with any of the respective Computational features. The highest correlation between the Rated features Timbre, Rhythm and Harmony and the corresponding Computational features was between 0.31 and 0.46. This explains why other studies [13, 19] extract features using different algorithms but

(a) A Plot of Rated Energy and Valence

(b) A Plot of the Emotive Descriptors

Figure 4: Scatter plots displaying the distribution of the Rated emotion components $Energy_{Rated}$ and $Valence_{Rated}$ and the components of the emotive descriptors, $Energy_{Mood}$ and $Valence_{Mood}$.

return similar classification results.

4.3 Feature Modelling

As was also observed by Yang et al. [8], non-linear regression proved to be superior to the linear alternative to model human rated perceptual features. Table 1 displays the returned correlation coefficient values for the three regression algorithms. The models fared worst when only five features were included, while the optimal number of features was found to be between ten and twenty-five. In almost all cases, results for the non-linear models, that is, ANN and SVR, were very similar, with SVR faring slightly better. The worse performance of MLR may be attributed to leaving only the linearly correlating features for the model, so any non-linear relationship was not taken into account in this model. In all cases the best model was found to be through SVR.

Acceptable models were built through SVR for the majority of perceptual descriptors, as shown in Tables 1 and 2. The features with best inter-rater agreement, Dynamics and Speed, were modelled best, with correlation coeffi-

Modelled Feature	Model 1 MLR	Model 2 ANN	Model 3 SVR
Speed	0.82 (0.13)	0.88 (0.08)	0.89 (0.08)
Rhythm	0.74 (0.21)	0.77 (0.17)	0.80 (0.15)
Pitch	0.64 (0.22)	0.72 (0.21)	0.72 (0.22)
Modality	0.57 (0.25)	0.65 (0.21)	0.78 (0.15)
Harmony	0.48 (0.31)	0.47 (0.31)	0.54 (0.28)
Melody	No model better than baseline found.		
Dynamics	0.87 (0.09)	0.92 (0.06)	0.93 (0.06)
Articulation	0.67 (0.23)	0.67 (0.24)	0.69 (0.22)
Timbre	No model better than baseline found.		0.63 (0.18)

Table 1: Correlation coefficient (r) values for feature modelling using the three algorithms: MLR, ANN and SVR. No one algorithm stands out as significantly better than the rest though best values are obtained through SVR. The standard deviation is given in brackets.

Modelled Feature	Number of Features	RMSE
Speed	20	0.45 (0.10)
Rhythm	15	0.56 (0.18)
Pitch	15	0.68 (0.19)
Mode	20	0.61 (0.14)
Harmony	20	0.82 (0.16)
Melody	No model better than baseline found.	
Dynamics	25	0.37 (0.10)
Articulation	10	0.74 (0.14)
Timbre	10	0.83 (0.20)

Table 2: The number of features included in the best model and RMSE values for feature modelling through SVR. The standard deviation is given in brackets. The optimal number of computational features included in the model was found by altering the amount after feature selection. The model with the lowest RMSE and lowest number of features was chosen.

icients between observed and modelled values of 0.93 and 0.89 respectively. However, the RMSE values obtained for Timbre and Harmony (0.8) were hardly better than the baseline (1). Since these were not the features with worst inter-rater agreement, the reason for the bad results was attributed to a general mismatch between Computational and Rated features.

Computational features directly related to the Rated ones were selected through feature selection in the respective models in the majority of cases. However, a number of Computational features from other musical domains, particularly the spectral domain, were also selected in the models. These facts, in addition to the weak correlation between the respective Rated and Computational features confirm that though progress is being made in modelling of perceptual musical descriptors, approximating a single computational feature to its perceptual equivalent is still an open research question.

Emotive Component	Rated	Modelled	Computational
Valence _{Rated}	0.95 (0.05)	0.57 (0.24)	0.68 (0.20)
Energy _{Rated}	0.98 (0.01)	0.89 (0.08)	0.86 (0.09)
Valence _{Mood}	0.87 (0.09)	0.53 (0.30)	0.61 (0.26)
Energy _{Mood}	0.95 (0.04)	0.87 (0.09)	0.85 (0.10)

Table 3: Correlation coefficient (r) values for the modelled components of emotion using three separate feature sets. The Valence component consistently returns weaker results, but are significantly better for the Rated feature set. Values for the standard deviation are included in brackets.

4.4 Emotion Classification

4.4.1 Regression

Table 3 displays the correlation coefficient values for the different feature sets used for modelling the emotion components. Better results were obtained for Energy_{Rated} and Valence_{Rated} when compared to Energy_{Mood} and Valence_{Mood} respectively. This can be explained by the similarity in rating method of the former pair to the remaining features.

For all components, the best feature set is the Rated one. Worse results were obtained for the Modelled and Computational feature sets. While results for the Energy components, with correlation coefficient values above 0.85, are acceptable, r values for the Valence components, particularly in the Modelled feature set (less than 0.6) are weak. Moreover, while for the Energy components, the Modelled feature set fared slightly better than the Computational one, for the Valence components, it fared slightly worse.

The difference in performance between the Energy and Valence dimensions is explained by which features affect the respective dimension. The highest ranking features for the Energy components, Speed and Dynamics, were the ones which were best modelled in the previous phase (with r values of 0.89 and 0.93 respectively). Results for the models of the three main predictors for Valence were not as good. While a model for Melody was not built due to high RMSE values, models for Timbre and Harmony, had the lowest r (0.63, 0.54) and highest RMSE (0.83, 0.82) values. Despite this high margin of error, these models were used to compile the Modelled feature set.

Better results obtained for the Energy component means that the ambiguity and difficulty in MER brought about by the subjectivity of emotions is focused in the Valence dimension, since accurate results can be and have been achieved with current algorithms in the Energy dimension. Still, Valence_{Rated} reached an r value of 0.95 for the Rated feature set. This means that accurate modelling is possible with the right feature set. However, such values have not been reached using Computational features. The problem therefore lies in identifying the Computational features that can accurately model the perceptual features effecting Valence. Though still complex, modelling a perceptual feature of a song is still less subjective than modelling its positivity.

Cluster	Feature Set		
	Rated	Modelled	Computational
Energetic-Positive	95.8%	70.8%	83.3%
Calm-Positive	80.0%	20.0%	66.7%
Calm-Negative	82.4%	64.7%	52.9%
Energetic-Negative	85.7%	85.7%	85.7%
Average	86.0%	60.3%	72.2%

Table 4: Cluster accuracy for the Rated emotion components Energy_{Rated} and Valence_{Rated} obtained through the three feature sets.

Cluster	Feature Set		
	Rated	Modelled	Computational
Energetic-Positive	71.4%	76.2%	61.9%
Calm-Positive	64.7%	11.8%	76.5%
Calm-Negative	94.1%	76.5%	64.7%
Energetic-Negative	86.7%	80.0%	66.7%
Average	79.2%	61.1%	67.4%

Table 5: Cluster accuracy for the components of the emotion descriptors Energy_{Mood} and Valence_{Mood} obtained through the three feature sets.

4.4.2 Clustering

The above observations were confirmed by the clustering results, displayed in Tables 4 and 5. Average accuracy ranges between 60% and 88%. When the Valence dimension was removed, that is, combining negative and positive options and considering only the calm and energetic clusters, accuracy rate exceeded 90% for all feature sets.

As can be observed in Tables 4 and 5, the biggest misclassifications are located in the calm clusters. For the Modelled feature set, where the calm-positive cluster has the smallest accuracy, the music clips were clustered with the calm-negative clips. This shows a bigger disagreement on whether calmer songs are positive (relaxed) or negative (depressed). The results may indicate that this differentiation relies more on taste than the energetic equivalents. People who enjoy songs in the energetic-negative cluster, tend to still describe them as angry songs. However, people who enjoy calmer songs describe them as relaxed but for those who do not, they are depressive.

This further highlights that the subjectivity of emotions focused in the Valence dimension, is particularly present in calmer music. The better results obtained by the Rated feature sets when compared with the Computational and Modelled ones indicate the importance of focusing on the listener for efficient classification systems.

5. DISCUSSION

Though acceptable results were obtained in the subjective test, a more consistent inter-rater correlation across all musical descriptors is desirable to ensure accurate modelling. Since the ground truth is based on these ratings, improvement in model accuracy will be difficult if these are not optimal. The starting point is grasping the human per-

ceptual understanding through optimally constructed subjective tests. The dataset needs to be adapted to the concept being tackled to highlight variances and observe similarities throughout genres. Having a subjective test per modelled feature might also improve inter-rater correlation since participants will focus on identifying a single feature, rather than eleven different elements.

A more in-depth analysis of the computational algorithms needs to be performed, and where required, adjusted or new ones developed. From a perceptual point of view, the computational features need to be a derivative of the perceptual features rather than the other way round. For better perceptual accuracy, the computational features need to go beyond theoretical correctness as in classical music theory and get closer to what people understand by the descriptor. A good example of this is perceptual speed against theoretical tempo. As shown in [29], tempo alone cannot accurately represent perceptual speed.

The work described in this paper shows that perceptual machine learned models can accurately predict human perception of music. Models for Speed and Dynamics made use of features beyond their own musical domain, which rendered the prediction truly representative of the perceptual equivalent. Subsequently, these two models contributed positively to the energy component of emotion, resulting in high accuracy ($r = 0.89$). This means that the model developed in this study accurately estimated human understanding, implying a reduction in the semantic gap.

6. CONCLUSION

The process of breaking down music emotion recognition into subtasks for the identification of the perceptual components led to a clearer understanding of the problem at hand. This study found that the first step required to tackle subjectivity in music emotion is to focus on the perceptual predictors of the Valence component. Though still complex, modelling a perceptual feature should be less subjective than modelling positivity. Similarly, other higher level classification concepts, such as Location or Activity, are bound to human understanding. Hence, the pursuit of accurate modelling of perceptual features is a natural approach.

The analysis in this paper highlights future points of focus required for narrowing the semantic gap. Once accurate computational perceptual features are identified, the large number of currently existing computational features is reduced to a much smaller number, close to human understanding. Rated and computational features such as Speed, Dynamics, Brightness and Dissonance will be highly correlated such that one computational perceptual feature will accurately represent the respective Rated feature. At this stage, addressing classification of higher level concepts can be reduced to the identification of the best out of about ten features, thus heavily simplifying these tasks.

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